

Densities, viscosities and thermodynamic excess properties of ternary liquid mixtures of aniline + acetone + (benzene or + toluene or + carbon tetrachloride or + 1,4-dioxane) and their constituent binaries at 298.15 K

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Abstract : Densities and viscosities of ternary liquid mixtures of aniline + acetone + (benzene or + toluene or + carbon tetrachloride or + 1,4-dioxane) and their constituent binary mixtures, viz. aniline + acetone, aniline + benzene, acetone + benzene, aniline + toluene, acetone + toluene, aniline + carbon tetrachloride, acetone + carbon tetrachloride, aniline + 1,4-dioxane, acetone + 1,4-dioxane have been measured at 298.15 K over the entire composition range. The values of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and thermodynamic excess properties viz. excess molar volume (V^E) and excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) have been determined for binary and ternary liquid mixtures at 298.15 K and fitted by Redlich-Kister and Cibulka equations respectively. It is concluded that experimental values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ compare fairly well with the corresponding theoretical values predicted by Redlich-Kister and Cibulka equations for binary and ternary liquid mixtures respectively.

Keywords : Density, viscosity, liquid mixtures.

In continuation of our earlier work¹ on the study of thermodynamic excess properties and transport properties of binary liquid mixtures, the title study has been undertaken. The main thrust of the work is to correlate the experimentally determined viscosity deviation ($\Delta\eta$), the excess molar volume (V^E) and excess free energy of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) of the following ternary mixtures and their constituent binary liquid mixtures to their theoretical values obtained by Redlich-Kister and Cibulka equations respectively² :

(i) Aniline + acetone + benzene; aniline + acetone + toluene; aniline + acetone + carbon tetrachloride and aniline + acetone + 1,4-dioxane.

(ii) Aniline + acetone; aniline + benzene; acetone + benzene; aniline + toluene; acetone + toluene; aniline + carbon tetrachloride; acetone + carbon tetrachloride; aniline + 1,4-dioxane and acetone + 1,4-dioxane.

Results and discussion

The experimentally determined values of densities and viscosities of pure components have been compared with the literature values and presented in Table 1. It is seen that the experimental values compare fairly well with the

Table 1. Comparison of experimental densities and viscosities of pure liquids with literature values at 298.15 K

Pure liquid	ρ (g cm ⁻³)		η (mPa.s)		Ref.
	Expt.	Lit.	Expt.	Lit.	
Aniline	1.022	1.0217 ^a	3.8672	3.8500	12
Acetone	0.7807	0.7843	0.3121	0.2993	13
Benzene	0.8697	0.8727	0.6080	0.6030	14
Toluene	0.8605	0.8622	0.5641	0.5580	15
Carbon tetrachloride	1.5861	1.5852	0.9096	0.9128	14
1,4-Dioxane	1.0408	1.0222 ^b	1.1800	1.0937 ^b	16

^aAt 293.15 K. ^bAt 303.15 K.

literature values.

The viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$), excess molar volumes (V^E) and excess molar Gibbs free energies of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) for binary and ternary mixtures were determined using the following equations³.

$$\Delta\eta = \eta - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \eta_i \quad (1)$$

where x_i is the mole fraction of the i -th component and η_i and η refer to the viscosities of i -th pure component and

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of the mixtures,

$$V^E = V - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i V_i \quad (2)$$

where V_i represents the molar volume and x_i the mole fraction of the i -th component. The quantity V refers to the molar volume of the mixture which can be calculated from the mixture density (ρ), and the component molecular weight M_i as below :

$$V = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i M_i / \rho \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta G^{#E} = RT \left[\ln \eta V - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \ln \eta_i V_i \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where the letters have their usual significance.

Employing the above mentioned equations, the experimental densities (ρ), viscosities (η), viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and excess thermodynamic properties viz. the

excess molar volumes (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energies of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{#E}$) at 298.15 K have been determined over the entire range of composition. The representative data in respect of binary and ternary mixtures have been presented in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

The viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$), the excess molar volumes (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energies of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{#E}$) for the ternary mixtures were fitted to Cibulka's eq. (5).

$$Y^E = Y_{bin}^E + x_1 x_2 x_3 [B_1 + B_2 x_1 + B_3 x_2] \quad (5)$$

where,

$$Y_{bin}^E = Y_{12}^E + Y_{13}^E + Y_{23}^E \quad (6)$$

The function Y^E (for ij binary mixtures) is given by Redlich-Kister's eq. (7).

$$Y_{ij}^E = x_i x_j \sum_{p=0}^P A_p (x_i - x_j)^p \quad (7)$$

Table 2. Densities, viscosities, viscosity deviations and thermodynamic excess properties of constituent binary liquid mixtures at 298.15 K

x_1	x_2	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	V (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)
Aniline + acetone							
0.0000	1.0000	0.7808	0.3121	0.0000	74.384	0.0000	0.00
0.0833	0.9167	0.8002	0.3644	-0.2438	76.227	0.4400	-118.92
0.1692	0.8308	0.8193	0.4238	-0.4898	78.133	0.9000	-265.15
0.2591	0.7409	0.8408	0.5074	-0.7258	79.879	1.1337	-372.40
0.3523	0.6477	0.8625	0.6194	-0.9451	81.654	1.3399	-453.31
0.4492	0.5508	0.8850	0.7717	-1.1373	83.415	1.4700	-510.07
0.5502	0.4498	0.9085	0.9752	-1.2929	85.155	1.5100	-560.90
0.6556	0.3444	0.9345	1.2522	-1.3906	86.741	1.3223	-606.95
0.7653	0.2347	0.9614	1.6787	-1.3541	88.815	1.0500	-575.16
0.8805	0.1195	0.9917	2.2590	-1.1834	89.683	0.4800	-578.14
1.0000	0.0000	1.0210	3.8672	0.0000	91.215	0.0000	0.00
Acetone + benzene							
0.0000	1.0000	0.8650	0.6080	0.0000	90.301	0.0000	0.00
0.1185	0.8815	0.8569	0.6199	0.0858	88.384	-0.0302	418.88
0.2329	0.7671	0.8434	0.6552	0.1499	87.080	0.4857	747.33
0.3421	0.6579	0.8325	0.6592	0.1814	85.596	0.7400	935.63
0.4476	0.5524	0.8234	0.6439	0.1926	83.976	0.7994	1037.05
0.5481	0.4519	0.8147	0.6196	0.1936	82.397	0.8200	1091.32
0.6456	0.3544	0.8073	0.5773	0.1759	80.738	0.7120	1055.00
0.7392	0.2608	0.7998	0.5144	0.1366	79.146	0.6100	899.47
0.8295	0.1705	0.7929	0.4540	0.0990	77.558	0.4594	712.52
0.9160	0.0840	0.7868	0.3718	0.0386	75.952	0.2300	327.51
1.0000	0.0000	0.7808	0.3121	0.0000	74.385	0.0000	0.00

Table 3. Densities, viscosities, viscosity deviations and thermodynamic excess properties of ternary liquid mixtures at 298.15 K

x_1	x_2	x_3	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	V (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)
Aniline + acetone + benzene								
0.0492	0.0599	0.8910	0.8310	0.4929	-0.1842	93.113	3.7120	-360.00
0.0973	0.1186	0.7841	0.8659	0.5279	-0.1842	89.150	0.6484	-390.00
0.1437	0.1770	0.6792	0.8692	0.5628	-0.0260	88.260	0.6540	-340.00
0.1437	0.2335	0.5764	0.8709	0.5766	-0.3306	87.598	0.8398	-390.00
0.1901	0.2887	0.4759	0.8743	0.6200	-0.4234	86.772	0.8509	-320.00
0.2354	0.3430	0.3770	0.8776	0.6609	-0.4841	85.971	0.8731	-270.00
0.2800	0.3968	0.2797	0.8776	0.6898	-0.5456	85.487	1.2062	-260.00
0.3235	0.4491	0.1845	0.8810	0.7141	-0.6164	84.701	1.2127	-280.00
0.3664	0.5004	0.0918	0.8843	0.7618	-0.6905	83.927	1.2124	-220.00
0.4078	0.5008	0.0455	0.8910	0.8462	-0.7378	84.042	1.3067	-150.00
0.4536	0.4498	0.0460	0.9044	0.9203	-0.7724	84.780	1.1769	-240.00
0.5042	0.3439	0.0947	0.9194	1.0981	-0.8430	86.633	1.2926	-200.00
0.5614	0.2897	0.0957	0.9312	1.2704	-0.8407	87.573	1.3118	-147.00
0.6147	0.2345	0.0968	0.9430	1.4847	-0.8209	88.505	1.3249	-72.00
0.6687	0.1194	0.1480	0.9580	1.7144	-0.7610	90.522	1.4523	-160.00
0.7326	0.1194	0.0989	0.9647	1.8930	-0.7266	90.650	1.5446	-120.00
0.7816	0.0604	0.1000	0.9781	2.1980	-0.6755	91.519	1.4124	-91.00
0.8396	0.0604	0.0960	0.9848	2.4231	-0.5364	91.658	1.5050	-62.00
Aniline + acetone + carbon tetrachloride								
0.0526	0.0641	0.8833	1.5896	0.5795	-0.3402	90.896	-4.7999	-1049.43
0.1034	0.1259	0.7707	1.5710	0.6243	-0.3822	86.247	-7.7000	-962.47
0.1513	0.1863	0.6624	1.5305	0.6901	-0.3970	82.849	-9.4000	-774.74
0.1985	0.2439	0.5576	1.5101	0.7538	-0.4138	78.420	-12.2000	-660.77
0.2440	0.2992	0.4568	1.4903	0.7993	-0.4460	74.055	-14.9997	-629.26
0.2881	0.3529	0.3590	1.5184	0.9125	-0.4081	67.536	-19.9991	-500.00
0.3302	0.4050	0.2548	1.5065	0.9211	-0.4709	63.066	-22.9997	-620.08
0.3714	0.4552	0.1734	1.4581	0.9765	-0.4858	60.145	-24.4999	-566.51
0.4105	0.5037	0.0858	1.3275	1.0376	-0.4910	60.778	-22.5000	-360.00
0.4551	0.5025	0.0424	1.4039	1.2272	-0.4062	55.625	-27.3998	-307.00
0.5059	0.4513	0.0428	1.3973	1.3655	-0.4131	57.189	-26.6999	-292.00
0.5653	0.3462	0.0885	1.5140	1.6129	-0.3590	57.046	-28.8993	-400.00
0.6189	0.2917	0.0894	1.4681	1.7888	-0.3366	60.168	-26.6998	-348.24
0.6734	0.2362	0.0904	1.3832	1.9405	-0.3411	65.308	-22.5000	-286.00
0.7405	0.1207	0.1387	1.4406	2.2500	-0.2481	67.547	-22.4999	-405.62
0.7873	0.1203	0.0925	1.3665	2.3927	-0.2152	69.181	-20.6000	-344.00
0.8457	0.0608	0.0935	1.2591	2.4600	-0.3151	76.780	-14.0000	-384.85
0.8932	0.0606	0.0462	1.1787	2.6667	-0.2195	79.586	-10.8992	-244.00

where Y_{ij}^E is $\Delta\eta$ or V^E or $\Delta G^{#E}$, x_i denotes the mole fraction of component i of the ij mixture with $x_j = 1-x_i$, and A_p are the adjustable parameters.

In order to obtain the value of Y_{bin}^E [vide eq. (6)] the experimentally determined values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$

for the following binary mixtures have been used : aniline + acetone; aniline + benzene; acetone + benzene; aniline + toluene; acetone + toluene; aniline + carbon tetrachloride; acetone + carbon tetrachloride; aniline + 1,4-dioxane; acetone + 1,4-dioxane.

The experimental values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$ of the above binary mixtures were fitted in the Redlich-Kister's eq. (7) to obtain the values of adjustable parameters A_p by the method of least squares using a computer. These along with the standard deviation (σ) have been presented in Table 4. Using these calculated values of A_p the values of Y_{12}^E , Y_{13}^E and Y_{23}^E were obtained from eq. (7) on

substituting the values of corresponding mole fraction of the components. Having thus obtained the values of Y_{bin}^E , the experimental values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$ for ternary mixtures were fitted to Cibulka's eq. (5) to obtain the values of coefficients B_1 , B_2 and B_3 by the method of least squares. After having determined the values of coefficients B_1 , B_2 and B_3 the theoretical values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E

Table 4. Coefficients of Redlich-Kister's equation and the corresponding standard deviation (σ) for the binary mixtures at 298.15 K

Viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and excess functions (V^E)	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	A_6	A_7	σ
Aniline + acetone									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-3.497	-1.756	-0.722	-	-	-	-	-	0.0009
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-6.070	-0.341	4.119	-	-	-	-	-	0.0014
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-1131.6	-14.1	-1625.6	-773.2	8137.7	9370.3	-9804.0	-14038.4	0.1979
Acetone + benzene									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	0.790	-0.113	-0.106	-	-	-	-	-	0.0005
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-3.267	0.049	0.415	-	-	-	-	-	0.0014
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	4299.4	1366.1	903.2	-10092.8	-1000.6	35248.4	-40.4	-34589.3	0.6994
Aniline + benzene									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-3.109	-1.509	-0.569	-	-	-	-	-	0.0006
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-8.766	-0.611	0.985	-	-	-	-	-	0.0013
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-1823.3	250.2	903.2	-1095.9	261.0	3458.1	1033.6	-4925.9	0.7048
Aniline + toluene									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-1.832	-0.229	0.079	-	-	-	-	-	0.0016
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	5.852	2.727	3.587	-	-	-	-	-	0.0012
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	852.7	87.0	3410.9	-5511.5	-15766.5	30768.4	17468.0	-34525.4	0.9680
Acetone + toluene									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	0.362	-0.024	0.064	-	-	-	-	-	0.0047
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	3.267	-0.049	-0.415	-	-	-	-	-	0.0020
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	2940.7	-824.0	-314.9	34975.8	-67770.6	-66808.0	232233.2	-131779.4	0.8965
Aniline + carbon tetrachloride									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-2.009	-0.264	-0.007	-	-	-	-	-	0.0038
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	164.319	-7.668	1.657	-	-	-	-	-	0.0014
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	2995.1	-3175.2	-4689.8	40189.7	25956.7	-118504.6	-30801.4	105029.7	0.7468
Acetone + carbon tetrachloride									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	3.384	-0.386	-0.335	-	-	-	-	-	0.0020
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	140.989	-6.712	-27.526	-	-	-	-	-	0.0019
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	13582.0	-2305.7	7663.8	68496.7	-169182.8	-65923.2	453280.0	-292112.9	0.7560
Aniline + 1,4-dioxane									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-0.754	0.112	-0.026	-	-	-	-	-	0.0092
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	32.948	-0.891	1.484	-	-	-	-	-	0.0025
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	1435.2	-144.7	-1069.4	3367.2	5605.9	-11322.9	-6593.0	10603.7	0.7828
Acetone + 1,4-dioxane									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-0.200	-0.008	-0.029	-	-	-	-	-	0.0050
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	32.222	-2.907	-9.366	-	-	-	-	-	0.0016
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	1676.7	346.5	4956.7	-249.6	-44500.6	28380.2	82047.9	-74598.1	0.8532

and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ were obtained from eq. (5). The standard deviation in regard to the experimental and theoretical values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ for the ternary mixtures was obtained using the following expression⁴.

$$\sigma(Y^E) = \left[\frac{\sum(Y_{\text{expt.}}^E - Y_{\text{calc.}}^E)^2}{(n - p)} \right]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

where, Y^E is $\Delta\eta$ or V^E or $\Delta G^{\#E}$, n is the number of experimental data and p is the number of parameters in Cibulka's equation. The values of coefficients B_1 , B_2 , B_3 and $\sigma(\Delta\eta)/\sigma(V^E)/\sigma(\Delta G^{\#E})$ in respect of ternary mixtures are presented in Table 5. It is seen that the experimental values of $\Delta\eta$ or V^E or $\Delta G^{\#E}$ for the ternary liquid mixtures compare fairly well with those predicted by Cibulka's equation.

Table 5. Coefficients of Cibulka equation and the corresponding standard deviation (σ) for the ternary mixtures at 298.15 K

Viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and excess functions (Y^E)	B_1	B_2	B_3	σ
Aniline + Acetone + Benzene				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-9.524	28.736	1.522	0.004
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-34.268	64.945	-35.483	0.028
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-49907.3	64203.4	41293.8	0.890
Aniline + Acetone + Toluene				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	5.519	21.557	-5.723	0.002
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	45.26	-83.82	-124.67	0.025
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	26301.7	15572.0	-34608.6	0.674
Aniline + Acetone + Carbon tetrachloride				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-61.875	-2.678	59.019	0.004
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	1426.257	-1997.765	-2290.749	0.054
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-159220.119	-85395.879	128668.788	0.923
Aniline + Acetone + 1,4-Dioxane				
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-23.220	23.098	36.429	0.004
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	352.937	-444.189	-622.912	0.063
$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-50699.929	36268.933	80952.593	0.896

The variation of densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) of the ternary mixtures of aniline with acetone as the second (polar) component, and benzene/toluene/carbon tetrachloride/1,4-dioxane as the (non-polar) third component with the mole fraction of aniline x_1 is non-linear. This non-linear variation of ρ and η with the change of composition of ternary mixtures indicates the presence of molecular interactions⁵.

The non-idealities as reflected in mixture viscosities are expressed in terms of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$). It is seen the values of $\Delta\eta$ in respect of all the ternary mixtures are negative. The negative values of $\Delta\eta$ are the consequences of lower viscosity contribution of non-specific interactions in non-ideal mixtures⁶. For all the constituent binary mixtures, $\Delta\eta$ is negative over the whole composition range, except the binaries of acetone with benzene and toluene for which $\Delta\eta$ is positive. The positive values of $\Delta\eta$ in these mixtures can be interpreted in terms of strong interactions between unlike molecules, acetone and benzene; and acetone and toluene⁷.

It is found that the values of V^E in respect of ternary mixtures are positive over the entire range of the composition in respect of all the mixtures except the one involving aniline + acetone + carbon tetrachloride for which V^E is negative. For the constituent binary mixtures, the values of V^E are positive over the entire range of composition except for the binary mixtures of aniline + carbon tetrachloride, aniline + 1,4-dioxane and acetone + carbon tetrachloride for which the values of V^E are negative. The positive values of V^E may be attributed to dispersive interactions between unlike molecules in binary and ternary mixtures; while the negative values may be attributed to the intermolecular dipolar/induced dipolar interactions and geometrical fitting between the components of binary and ternary mixtures⁸.

The results of the study show that the values of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ are negative over the entire range of composition for all the ternary mixtures. The same is true for the constituent binaries except the mixtures of acetone with benzene and toluene for which $\Delta G^{\#E}$ is positive over the entire range of composition. The negative values of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ in the binary and ternary mixtures under discussion may be attributed to the dominance of dispersion forces while the positive values of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ observed in the binary mixtures of acetone + benzene and acetone + toluene may be ascribed to the size effect of the mixing components in these binaries⁹.

The plots of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ versus x_1 of the binary mixtures in each case have parabolic shape and are characterized by the presence of well-defined maxima/minima which indicate the presence of complex formation between the mixing components of binary mixtures¹⁰. In Fig. 1, as a graphical representation of data, plots of $\Delta\eta$ vs x_1 have been presented. The interactions in a ternary, $i + j + k$ mixture are closely dependent on the interactions in the constituent binaries $i + j$, $j + k$ and $i + k$ ¹¹. It should therefore be possible to correlate the nature of interactions occurring in ternary mixtures with those of

Fig. 1. Variation of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) with mole fraction x_1 of the first component in binary liquid mixture of (O) aniline + acetone, (\square) aniline + benzene, (\blacktriangle) acetone + benzene, (\blacksquare) aniline + toluene, (\triangle) acetone + toluene, (\bullet) aniline + carbon tetrachloride, ($*$) acetone + carbon tetrachloride, (\times) aniline + 1,4-dioxane and ($+$) acetone + 1,4-dioxane at 298.15 K.

binary mixtures. The fact that the binary mixtures are characterized by complex formation between their constituent components, it follows that the parabolic shape of the plots of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$ versus x_1 indicate that interactions occurring in the ternary mixtures of the title study are of specific nature.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the present study were of analytical grade.

Liquid mixtures of various compositions were prepared by mass in a 25 cm³ flask using a Mettler analytical balance. The uncertainty in the mole fraction of the mixtures was estimated to be less than ± 0.0001 . Density and viscosity measurements were carried out using a thermostatically controlled water bath (± 0.01 K).

Densities of pure liquids and their binary and ternary liquid mixtures were measured at 298.15 K with an Anton Parr digital vibrating tube densimeter. The uncertainty of the density measurements was estimated to be $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³. The viscosities (η) of pure organic liquids and their binary and ternary liquid mixtures were determined using an Ostwald viscometer which was suspended in a thermostat maintained at 298.15 ± 0.01 K. The details of the procedure have been reported in an earlier publication¹. The uncertainty of calculated absolute viscosities was $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ mPa.s.

References

1. M. Singh, P. C. Gupta and R. N. Kesharwani, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1995, **40**, 358; P. Jain and M. Singh, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2004, **49**, 214; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 225; D. Agarwal and M. Singh, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2004, **49**, 1218; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 850.
2. O. Redlich and A. T. Kister, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1948, **40**, 345; I. Cibulka, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1982, **47**, 1414.
3. M. Dominguez, J. Santafe, M. C. Lopez, F. M. Royo and J. S. Urieta, *Fluid Phase Equilib.*, 1998, **152**, 133; M. M. Palaologou, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1996, **41**, 1036.
4. M. Dominguez, J. I. Parel, I. Gascon and F. M. Royo, *Fluid Phase Equilib.*, 2000, **169**, 277.
5. B. K. Rout, S. K. Dash, V. Chakravorty and D. Behera, *Indian J. Technology*, 1996, **31**, 745; N. Swain and V. Chakravorty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 395; B. K. Rout and V. Chakravorty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 303.
6. N. Swain, V. Chakravorty, S. K. Singh and D. Pandey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 1116.
7. N. Swain and V. Chakravorty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 395.
8. H. C. Ku and C. H. Tu, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2005, **50**, 608.
9. S. L. Oswal and A. V. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 1026.
10. C. Yong, P. Ma and Q. Zhou, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2004, **49**, 881.
11. J. L. Zurita, D. A. Guriel and M. A. Dastigo, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1992, **37**, 206.
12. D. R. Lide, "Hand Book of Organic Solvents", CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 1995.
13. A. D. Tripathi, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1995, **40**, 1262; J. Nath and A. P. Dixit, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1984, **29**, 317.
14. B. B. Gurung, A. Chaudhury and M. N. Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 330.
15. P. S. Nikam and S. J. Kharat, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2005, **50**, 455.
16. M. Contreras, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2001, **46**, 1149.